

Some identities involving the k -th power complements

Yanni Liu and Jinping Ma

Department of Mathematics, Northwest University
Xi'an, Shaanxi, P.R.China

Abstract The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the calculating problem of one kind infinite series involving the k -th power complements, and obtain several interesting identities.

Keywords k -th power complements; Identities; Riemann-zeta function.

§1. Introduction and Results

For any given natural number $k \geq 2$ and any positive integer n , we call $a_k(n)$ as a k -th power complements, if $a_k(n)$ is the smallest positive integer such that $n \cdot a_k(n)$ is a perfect k -th power. That is,

$$a_k(n) = \min\{m : mn = u^k, u \in N\}.$$

Especially, we call $a_2(n), a_3(n), a_4(n)$ as the square complement number, cubic complement number, and the quartic complement number, respectively. In reference [1], Professor F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the k -th power complement number sequence. About this problem, there are many people have studied it, see references [4], [5], and [6]. For example, Lou Yuanbing [7] gave an asymptotic formula involving the square complement number $a_2(n)$. Let real number $x \geq 3$, he proved that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} d(a_2(n)) = c_1 x \ln x + c_2 x + O(x^{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon}),$$

where $d(n)$ is the divisor function, $\varepsilon > 0$ be any fixed real number, c_1 and c_2 are defined as following:

$$c_1 = \frac{6}{\pi^2} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(p+1)^2}\right),$$

$$c_2 = \frac{6}{\pi^2} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(p+1)^2}\right) \left(\sum_p \frac{2(2p+1) \ln p}{(p-1)(p+1)(p+2)} + 2\gamma - 1\right),$$

γ is the Euler's constant, \prod_p denotes the product over all primes.

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In reference [8], Yao Weili obtained an asymptotic formula involving k -th power complement number $a_k(n)$. That is, for any real number $x \geq 1$, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} d(na_k(n)) = x(A_0 \ln^k x + A_1 \ln^{k-1} x + \dots + A_k) + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}),$$

where A_0, A_1, \dots, A_k are computable constant, ε is any fixed positive number.

In reference [4], Zhang Wenpeng obtained some identities involving the k -th power complements. Those are, for any complex numbers s with $Re(s) \geq 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(na_2(n))^s} &= \frac{\zeta^2(2s)}{\zeta(4s)}, \\ \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(na_3(n))^s} &= \frac{\zeta^2(3s)}{\zeta(6s)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{3s} + 1}\right), \\ \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(na_4(n))^s} &= \frac{\zeta^2(4s)}{\zeta(8s)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{4s} + 1}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{4s} + 2}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function.

On the other hand, F.Russo [9] proposed 21 unsolved problems, the problem 19 asked us evaluate the infinite series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{a_2(n)}.$$

But is problem very easy. In fact, $a_2(4n^2) = 1$ for all positive integer n . So we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (-1)^{4n^2} \frac{1}{a_2(4n^2)} = 1 \neq 0.$$

That is, the infinite series $\sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{a_2(n)}$ dos not convergent.

In this paper, we shall use the elementary method to study the calculating problem of the infinite series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{na_k(n)},$$

and obtain several interesting identities for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. For any given positive integer $k \geq 2$, we have the identity

$$\sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{na_k(n)} = \frac{2^k - k - 1}{2^k + k - 1} \zeta(k) \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{p^k}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann-zeta function, and \prod_p denotes the product over all different primes.

Taking $k = 2$ in our theorem, and note that the fact $\zeta(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$, $\zeta(4) = \frac{\pi^4}{90}$ and

$$\prod_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^2}\right) = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^4}\right) \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2}\right)^{-1} = \frac{\zeta(2)}{\zeta(4)},$$

we may immediately obtain the following:

Corollary 1. For the square complement number $a_2(n)$, we have the identity

$$\sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{na_2(n)} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Corollary 2. For the cubic complement number $a_3(n)$, we have the identity

$$\sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{na_3(n)} = \frac{2}{5} \zeta(3) \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{2}{p^3}\right).$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorem. For all positive integers n , we separate n into three parts: $2 \nmid n$; $2 \mid n$ and $2^k \nmid n$; $2^k \mid n$. Then from the definition of $a_k(n)$ we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{na_k(n)} &= \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{na_k(n)} - \sum_{\alpha=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\beta=1}^{k-1} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2^{\alpha k + \beta n}) a_k(2^{\alpha k + \beta n})} \\ &\quad - \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2^{\alpha k n}) a_k(2^{\alpha k n})} \\ &= \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{na_k(n)} - \sum_{\alpha=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\beta=1}^{k-1} \frac{1}{2^{(\alpha+1)k}} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{na_k(n)} - \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{\alpha k}} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{na_k(n)} \\ &= \frac{2^k - k - 1}{2^k - 1} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{na_k(n)}. \end{aligned}$$

It is clear that the infinite series $\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{na_k(n)}$ is absolutely convergent, so from the Euler product formula (see Theorem 11.6 of [2]) we know that the infinite series can be expressed as an absolutely convergent infinite product. That is,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ 2 \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{na_k(n)} &= \prod_{\substack{p \\ p \neq 2}} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{pa_k(p)} + \frac{1}{p^2 a_k(p^2)} + \dots \right\} \\ &= \prod_{\substack{p \\ p \neq 2}} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p^l a_k(p^l)} \\ &= \prod_{\substack{p \\ p \neq 2}} \left(\sum_{\alpha=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\beta=1}^{k-1} \frac{1}{p^{\alpha k + \beta} a_k(p^{\alpha k + \beta})} + \sum_{\alpha=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p^{\alpha k} a_k(p^{\alpha k})} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \prod_{\substack{p \\ p \neq 2}} \left(\sum_{\alpha=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\beta=1}^{k-1} \frac{1}{p^{(\alpha+1)k}} + \sum_{\alpha=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p^{\alpha k}} \right) \\
&= \prod_{\substack{p \\ p \neq 2}} \frac{p^k + k - 1}{p^k - 1} \\
&= \prod_p \frac{1 + \frac{k-1}{p^k}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^k}} \cdot \frac{1 - \frac{1}{2^k}}{1 + \frac{k-1}{2^k}} \\
&= \frac{2^k - 1}{2^k + k - 1} \zeta(k) \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{p^k} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

So we have

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{na_k(n)} = \frac{2^k - k - 1}{2^k + k - 1} \zeta(k) \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{p^k} \right).$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

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